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MESS 0003

MIMS 2.21.1 : the Literal Union of the 5 and 8; a pre-MIMS Diagrammatica
Explained

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ABSTRACT

The following MESSy analysis makes use of pre-EPEMC (extended plasma-electromagnetic cosmology) work which had a *mimsical* bent to it, to begin the process of finding a more “universal” Unified Cosmology. The inductive and deductive work, occasionally even empirical, will be combined back within the EPEMC framework (hence MESSy standard¹) to create a forward-backward east-west syncretic, even synesthetic (and æsthetic) description which explains not only what we find in physics, natural philosophæ, æthereal mechanics², etc. but *why* we see the results (eg. why our technocracy is poisoning the world). This paper follows on the MIMS 2.21 foundation³, looking at the Union of the five phases and ancillary diagrammatica, and the eight laws (“bagua dharma”), we well established pre/post MIMSy.

Keywords: MIMS - Aether - Karma - Bagua - Dharma - Cosmology - Vedas - Multiverse

¹ https://www.academia.edu/87222389/MIMS_1_04_1_05_MESS0001

² Remember: in EPEMC the plasma-electromagnetic force-field (the “sea of [fractal] charge” is the Unified Aether Field https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC

³ https://www.academia.edu/86538573/MIMS_2_21_The_Union_of_the_5_and_8

MIMS 2.21.1 - The Supreme Diagrammatica

Figure 1: the “Tai Yuan Bagua Tu” 太原八卦图; credit: the author⁴
“Ayurveda, Greek, and Chinese Elements Combined to match the 8 Laws” (sic)

The cited text, which was pre-EPEMC, and therefore pre-MIMS (and yet performing the same actions!) says,

“...Actually both are correct. It is also OK to be either one.

And both can lose the Mandate of Heaven just as they can lose the Te. The Nei Yeh says that the amount of Te in the person is directly proportionate to the amount of Zeng (chest) Qi. The Zeng Qi comes from Ancestral Qi (air), which of course is related to the Righteous Qi as it is inherited from Heaven. Hence the Te is related to Righteousness and has an implication similar to Li - moral authority. This supports the idea that Karma is related to one's Virtuosity. ... However, there is no support - from a normal person's perspective of bills and taxes and kids - for the idea that Te alone will enhance one's karmic data stream. Many sages and scholars have been killed for being too virtuous. Many idiots and evil men have lived full lives with cold hearts and ignorant closed minds. The Mandate of Heaven is gifted and taken away by the “wordless pronouncement” according to some chaotic and grand design that seems, after all, WAY beyond human comprehension. Beautiful children have been murdered just as well as tyrants like Stalin put up with for decades.” (sic, p. 15)

These are topics that have come up in MIMS before, under higher standards of citation and proof. There is no standard definition in EPEMC for “karmic data stream”, but it was discussed in a recent episode of

⁴ Lit: Greatest Original Eight Trigram Diagram

the Pulse⁵. Essentially, this is an idea out of “Triple-Plane Theory,” (TPT, p.5) which doesn’t have a MESSy or a MIMS paper to begin with! Again, it was described, in brief, in the Bagua Dharma⁶ (pre-EPEMC) and the cited paper. It is the origin of the mimsical idea of the PPPC⁷, as well as a number of descriptions of means of unsubstantiated parallel Universe hypothesis, etc. Its ties to the Buddhist-Dharmic “samsara”⁸ experience notwithstanding, geometrically the 3D Universe is related to the TPT directly, in the same way that three-legged tables stand on all 3D surfaces while 4D ones do not⁹. The particular fractalitic and relativistic geometry of our particular Uni-multiverse, as proposed in the pre-EPEMC, is described in the Dougherty Set, as well as by the author in many pre-EPEMC works. Nevertheless, what’s important here is that the Aether, Mandate of Heaven (Heaven’s Will + your life-contract), the Qi (life-charge or vapours), and the Dao are all unified under a grand *dharmic* diagrammatica¹⁰, which reminds the author of another important diagram.

The two are not directly related, nor are they unrelated. It will be up to the astute observer to combine the two.

Diagrammatica Explained

The Eight Laws (Bagua Dharma) are explained elsewhere¹¹. Suffice it to say all the 5 phases (and therefore 5 Forces of Life/regions) and the “Big G” are combined with the Eight Laws directly, performing, perhaps more efficiently, the work of this paper’s predecessor. It will be up to the 2.21.X series to test the conformity of the 5 Forces with the 8 laws, using this diagrammatica, in order to prove with some great degree above doubt, that the diagram really is the Great Original, or if it was just another ‘bright idea’. ie, is it a MIMS, or not?

Figure 2 - Number Theory

Summary

The 2.21.X series will put forth a series of analyses. Some will be MESSy, and some full MIMSical analyses, but the true purpose is into understanding the 1) torsion 2) viability 3) Correlation 4) Causation 5) Dharmic 6) Physical 7) Numerical 8) Mystical and 9) Magikal utility of the Tai Sheng Bagua Tu.

⁵ <https://rumble.com/v1ldcih-the-pulse-episode-82-the-mims-of-the-planet-gods-...-do-they-talk-to-us.html>

⁶ https://www.academia.edu/50804985/Trigram_Law_Bagua_Dharma_Short_document_single_page_reference & https://www.academia.edu/50804995/Bagua_Dharma_Lectures_1_and_2

⁷ Possibility-Potentiality-Probability-Cloud; which exists prior to Causational Fate (due to Conservation) collapsing the waveform into a single potential we call *Substantiated* (and therefore ‘real’ = ~100% probable)

⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/samsara>

⁹ <https://uh.edu/engines/epi2533.htm>

¹⁰ Literally a purpose under God.

¹¹ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

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